

Institutional Review Board Office

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Website: www.bsph.edu/irb

APPROVAL/DETERMINATION MEMO
INITIAL APPLICATION

Date: July 2, 2024

To: Maria Elena Figueroa, PhD
Department of Health, Behavior & Society

From: Anna Durbin, MD
Chair, IRB- FC

Study Title: “Evaluation of prototype solutions for optimizing IFA or MMS adherence among pregnant women and adolescent girls in Ethiopia”

IRB No.: 24717

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Approved <input type="checkbox"/> Approved, minor change (single reviewer) <input type="checkbox"/> Approved Expedited Cat: <input type="checkbox"/> Determined to be Exempt Cat:	Approval/Determination Date: May 8, 2024 Approval Lapse Date: May 7, 2025
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As Principal Investigator for this IRB approved study, you are responsible for conducting the study in accordance with the ethical principles of the Belmont Report, in compliance with all relevant laws and regulations, and in accordance with JHU institutional policy.

Your approval will LAPSE on May 7, 2025. This means you cannot perform study activities after this date without an approved progress report. If you submit less than 1 week before the lapse date, the IRB may not be able to review your report and process an approval in time to avoid a lapse. We recommend that you submit a progress report 6 weeks before the approval lapse date to avoid an interruption to your research operations.

This approval is inclusive of the following documentation:

Research Plan:

- Ethiopia IFA-MMS Research Plan (PI version #1, June 27, 2024)

Consent/Parental Permission/Assent Form(s):

- Informed Consent Form – Ethiopia Consent IDI Adult Pregnant Women; IRB approval date; May 8, 2024; (PI version #1, April 26, 2024)
- Informed Consent Form – Ethiopia Consent IDI Adult Pregnant Women; IRB approval date; May 8, 2024; (PI version#1, April 26, 2024 – Amh)
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- Informed Consent Form – Ethiopia Consent IDI Adult Pregnant Women; IRB approval date; May 8, 2024; (PI version#1, April 26, 2024 – Wol)
- Informed Consent Form - Ethiopia IFA-MMS Consent Adult Quantitative Baseline (PI version#1, April 26, 2024)
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- Informed Consent Form – Ethiopia Adult Consent Quantitative Endline; IRB approval date; May 8, 2024; (PI version#1, April 26, 2024)
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- Parental Permission – Ethiopia Pregnant Women Baseline; IRB approval date; May 8, 2024; (PI version#1, April 26, 2024)
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- Assent Form – Ethiopia Assent Adolescent Pregnant Women Baseline; IRB approval date; May 8, 2024; (PI version#1, April 26, 2024)
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- Assent Form – Ethiopia Assent Adolescent Pregnant Women Endline; IRB approval date; May 8, 2024; (PI version#1, April 26, 2024 - Wol)

Recruitment Material:

- Ethiopia FIA-MMS Recruitment Script – KII Qualitative; IRB approval date; May 8, 2024; (PI version #1, March 23, 2024)
- Ethiopia IFA-MMS Recruitment Script – Pregnant Women Quantitative; IRB approval date; May 8, 2024; (PI version#1, March 24, 2024)
- Ethiopia Recruitment Script – Pregnant Women IDI; IRB approval date; May 8, 2024; (PI version#1, March 19, 2024)

Instruments:

- Form 1; Monitoring Tracking Sheets and Checklist;
- Form 2; Supportive Supervision and Monitoring Tracking and Checklist;
- Ethiopia IFA-MMS IDI PW; (PI version#1, March 26, 2024)
- Ethiopia IFA-MMS KII Guide HDAs; (PI version#1, March 25, 2024)
- Ethiopia IFA-MMS KII Guides HEWs Midwives Nurses; (PI version#1, March 25, 2024)

- Ethiopia IFA-MMS KII Guides PHCU MCH; (PI version#1, March 25, 2024)
- Women Questionnaire IFA MMS; (March 28, 2024)

<p>*DHHS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 45 CFR 46 <input type="checkbox"/> CR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Revised CR</p> <p>FDA <input type="checkbox"/> 21 CFR 50, 56 <input type="checkbox"/> IND, 21 CFR 312 <input type="checkbox"/> IDE, 21 CFR 812</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> IND/IDE held by BSPH PI <input type="checkbox"/> Dept. of Defense Funding <input type="checkbox"/> Min. Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Greater than min. risk</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> GWAS <input type="checkbox"/> Reliance Agreement <input type="checkbox"/> Clinical Trial/GCP</p> <p>*Study Site(s): <input type="checkbox"/> U.S. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> International</p> <p>*List Country(ies): Ethiopia</p>	<p>*Consent/Parental Permission Required From: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Adult Participant <input type="checkbox"/> LAR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> One Parent <input type="checkbox"/> Two Parents 46.406, 50.53 <input type="checkbox"/> Legal Guardian of Children in Foster Care <input type="checkbox"/> Minor Consent as Adult</p> <p>*Vulnerable Populations: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Children <input type="checkbox"/> Foster Care Children</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>DHHS</td> <td>FDA</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 46.404</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> 50.51</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> 46.405</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> 50.52</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> 46.406</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> 50.53</td> </tr> </table> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Preg. Women/Fetuses 46.204 <input type="checkbox"/> Neonates <input type="checkbox"/> Prisoners</p>	DHHS	FDA	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 46.404	<input type="checkbox"/> 50.51	<input type="checkbox"/> 46.405	<input type="checkbox"/> 50.52	<input type="checkbox"/> 46.406	<input type="checkbox"/> 50.53	<p>*Adult Consent: <input type="checkbox"/> Written Consent <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Waiver of Signature <input type="checkbox"/> Exempt (Electronic) <input type="checkbox"/> Alteration of Consent; meets 46.116 (f)(3) criteria <input type="checkbox"/> Waiver of Informed Consent; meets 46.116 (f)(3) criteria</p> <p>*Assent: <input type="checkbox"/> Written (signed) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Oral <input type="checkbox"/> Statement in Parent Permission Form <input type="checkbox"/> Electronic <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Waived for all children <input type="checkbox"/> Waived for children</p> <p>*HIPAA: <input type="checkbox"/> JHM <input type="checkbox"/> Non-JHM <input type="checkbox"/> Authorization <input type="checkbox"/> Prep. To Research <input type="checkbox"/> HIPAA Alteration/Waiver <input type="checkbox"/> JHM Data Tracking <input type="checkbox"/> Limited Data Set <input type="checkbox"/> DUA</p>	<p>*Parental Permission: <input type="checkbox"/> Written Permission <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Waiver of Signature <input type="checkbox"/> Exempt (Electronic) <input type="checkbox"/> Alteration of Permission; meets 46.116 (f)(3) criteria <input type="checkbox"/> Waiver of Permission; <input type="checkbox"/> Meets 46.116 (f)(3) <input type="checkbox"/> 46.408, with Substitute Mechanism provided</p> <hr/> <p>*Sample Size: (screened plus enrolled) 5,096</p> <p>*Final Enrollment:</p> <p>*Secondary Data Analysis: (specimens/participants)</p>
DHHS	FDA										
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 46.404	<input type="checkbox"/> 50.51										
<input type="checkbox"/> 46.405	<input type="checkbox"/> 50.52										
<input type="checkbox"/> 46.406	<input type="checkbox"/> 50.53										

*Complete for Exempt Studies for operational purposes to help track documents; HSR code provisions do not apply.

As Principal Investigator of IRB approved research, you are responsible for meeting the following requirements of approval:

- 1) Informing the co-investigators listed on the application of the status of the research.
- 2) Submitting an Amendment Application or Administrative Amendment for any changes in research. These changes in research are required to be reviewed and approved prior to the activation of the changes unless you are correcting or clarifying language in approved instruments.
- 3) Reporting Unanticipated problems involving risk of harm to participants or others that are related to the study procedures to the BSPH IRB within 10 days of the time that the PI learns of such problems. A Problem Event Report Form must be submitted to the IRB immediately.
- 4) Using only the most recently approved BSPH IRB approved consent forms, with the BSPH stamp or logo, unless otherwise approved by the IRB. All consent forms signed by subjects enrolled in the study should be stored securely, in paper or electronic form, until 3 years following study completion unless otherwise approved by the IRB.

5) Submitting in a timely fashion Continuing Review Applications or Progress Reports. The Approval Lapse Date above marks the end of this approval; no study activity may take place after that date without new IRB approval. Submit your report to the IRB Office no later than six weeks prior to the approval lapse date to allow time for IRB review to be completed prior to that date.

6) If your study is an NIH funded clinical trial, e.g., “A research study in which one or more human participants are prospectively assigned to one or more interventions (which may include placebo or other control) to evaluate the effects of those interventions on health-related biomedical or behavioral outcomes”, it must be registered on clinicaltrials.gov, and one IRB approved consent form used in the study must be posted on a publicly available Federal website.

8) If your research involves a Reliance Agreement through which we are serving as the Reviewing IRB, you are responsible for informing the relying PI of the initial approval, and any amendment or continuing review approvals.

AD/rch